

Effect of Flipped Strategy on Achievement in Algebraic Concepts among Secondary School Students in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of flipped strategy on achievement in algebra concepts among secondary school students in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State. Quasi- experimental research design was adopted for the study. The target population of the study consist of included all government senior secondary school class two (SSII) students in Ikom education zone during 2021/2022 academic session. A total sample of senior secondary school (SSII) students of forty-five males (45) and thirty-eight females (38) was used for the study Purposive multi-stage random sampling technique (stratified and simple sampling) was used to composed the sample. Three research objectives and questions guided the study, alongside with corresponding three hypotheses which was tested at 0.05 significance level. The study used Students Mathematics Achievement Test (SMAT). The instrument was developed by the researchers. The SELMQ consisting of 16 items to assess the effective participation of students in learning mathematics which was developed by the researchers. It has 4-point Likert type response scale in which respondents were expected to indicate in the column against each of the item The SMAT was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was established by the use of Kuder-Richardson K-21 to obtain an index of 0.85 used of Kuder-Richardson K-21. The research question were answered using Descriptive statistics, analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The finding revealed that flipped classroom instructional strategy has a significantly greater effect on students' academic achievement in Mathematics than the teacher-centered approach. Based on the results of the findings, it was recommended among others that Cross River State Secondary school education board should deemed implementing the flipped classroom instructional strategy in Mathematics as it engages students dedication, interest and motivation in learning.

Keywords: Flipped Classroom Strategy, Achievement, Mathematics, Instruction & Students

Introduction

It has been established that mathematics started with the ancient Egyptians and Babylonians and expanded by the Greeks into a systematic study programme. The origin and history of Mathematics is traced back to the prehistoric times when hunters created language to record multiple kills or objects (Kytherine Thomas, 2020). This provided early man with a structure as he attempted to keep tract of his belongings, such as number of arrowheads he had, how many wives he had, how many people were in his household and how many children had been born and older members had died. He probably even wanted to know how many chickens he now had after the last hatch. This humble beginning of Mathematics gave rise to today's formal counting of numbers, which are basic to Mathematics concepts studied in educational constructs (Enukoha, 2010).

Mathematics is one of the compulsory disciplines in the Nigerian educational system. This subject is very relevance and vital in people's lives and its impacts in almost everything one does for survival in the society. Anaduaka and Okafor (2013) noted that an individual can get on sometime without knowing how to read and write, but can never push on smoothly without knowing how to count, measure, add and subtract. This statement above supported what Akusoba and Okeke (2009)

said, the importance of Mathematics in human endeavours cannot be over-emphasized with the fact that people use Mathematics consciously or unconsciously in various aspects of life.

It therefore goes without argument that in anything man does on this planet earth, there must be an element of Mathematical linkage which might be needed in order to accomplish that task effectively achieved. In a quest to discover ways of enhancing the teaching and learning of Mathematics, it is therefore pertinent and needful to foster innovative teaching approach or strategy and improve students' interest and academic achievement in Mathematics for secondary school students to be awakened to the relevant and develop authentic foundation in the knowledge of Mathematics, there is need for practical, hands-on and minds-on activities in Mathematics lessons, active participation of the students in the process has the potential to build students understanding and interest which enhances academic achievement in Mathematics.

However, flipped instructional strategy in classroom, is a pedagogical approach of teaching where home works are done at school and school works done at home (Charles-Organ & Williams, 2015), flipped instructional classroom strategy is a strategy whereby students assess instructional video prepared by the instructor prior to the classroom sessions and use class time to participate in meaningful learning activities in which instructor guided problem solving and discussion (Strayer, 2007; Bergman, Overmyer & Willies, 2013). Flipped classroom strategy is an educational instructional approach whereby learners view pre-recorded teaching using technological devices at home, library environment or any place where the materials for instruction are made accessible (Alvalz, 2012; Bergman & Sam, 2012; Fulton, 2012). The teacher would require the students to have completed the assigned works, prepare for discussions and explanations of the concepts they have studied in preparation for the next lesson, here what the students have normally done at home is now becoming what they do in class. For indications, the flipped instructional classroom strategy is a new innovative teaching and learning strategy in Nigerian educational system which emphasized student-centredness as against teacher-centredness methods to teaching and learning. Saunders (2014) explained that pedagogical pattern of the teacher is very important to students' academic achievement and it can greatly impact on the way students view a particular subject and even education as a whole, he observed that teachers represent their subjects anytime and everywhere and so, the way they teach would encourage or discourage the students from studying the subjects. Anaduaka and Okafor (2013) observed that a dedicated Mathematics teacher should be able to take his/her students to the level they would begin to appreciate Mathematics, its beauty and its application so that students' attitude towards the subject would begin to change positively, Mathematics Academic Achievement (MAA) would imply the achievement of students' score on standardized tests and scores obtained from class and external examination while students' academic performance are basically on general aptitude and the competencies that are the outcomes of good behaviour in the school environment (Maduewes, 2005).

This implies that the flipped instructional classroom should promote academic achievement of students in Mathematics, also enhances students' effective learning in the school system. Many proponents of flipped instructional classroom strategy are (Foertech, Moses, Strikwerda & Litzkow, 2002; Swenson & Lents, 2012, Kay & Kletskin, 2012) were emphatic in advocating that flipped instructional classroom strategy has the capacity of inculcating in the students problem-solving, critical thinking and inquiry skills which are cardinal in attaining high academic achievement in Mathematics subjects in Nigeria secondary schools. However, in view of these, flipped instructional classroom strategy would help to make available diverse activities that would help in facilitating the relevance of Mathematics lesson, sensitize students' effective study and learning of Mathematics which could enhance students' academic achievement.

Vaughan (2014) studied pre-service teachers' perceptions of the flipped model of instruction as an instructional strategy to reach a classroom full of millennial learners. The author argued that millennial learners, also known as digital natives, often have access to information at their fingertips and prefer to learn in active and collaborative environments. Also Vaughan (2014) stated that flipped model of instruction provides educators with the means to integrate effective use of technology in their classrooms to promote an active, collaborative environment. The results of the study revealed that flipped classroom improves students' engagement, increase students-teacher feedback and promote self-pace learning among students.

Also, Kaushai, Chang-Nan and Chunyen (2015) in their study the impact of flipped classroom on Mathematics concept learning in high school used a pre-test, post-test, quasi experimental design. They used 82 high school students aged between 14-15 years for the study. The experimental group was 41 (28 male and 13 female) and the control group 41 (24 male and 17 female). They categorized the achievers in each group into high, average and low. Those students who scored 75-100 were termed high achievers, those in the bracket of 60-74 were categorized into average achievers while those below 60 were marked as low achievers. The experimental group was taught trigonometry using the flipped classroom strategy whereas the control group did the same lesson using the conventional learning strategy. The researchers gave both groups a pre-test and posttest with the intention to determine if the learning outcome would be the same using the same instructor. The result showed that

the students in experimental group who used flipped classroom strategy performed much better than those who were taught in controlled group. Besides, the study threw more light on the performance of low achievers in the experimental group. Also, their performance was far better than the control group and the performance of high and average achievers remained constant (Bidwell, 2014). The study has proven that flipped classroom has great potentials in improving teaching and learning of Mathematics.

In another work, Kadry and ElHani (2014) used flipped classroom model method for calculus II. The students' performances in the examination were used to assess the scores from 0-100 points. The number of participants who completed the quiz was 120. The performance of the students in the flipped classroom was better than the traditional approach. The performance between male and female model for 60 students was examined. The females in the flipped classroom model performed better. Although the mean scores were higher in the flipped classrooms, the t-test for independent samples proved that the difference in the means between the groups were not significant ($p > .05$) different. Also, Schultz, et al. (2013) carried out research on effects of flipped classroom model on students' performance for advanced placement high school chemistry students. The research made use of mixed method approach comprising quantitative and qualitative techniques. They used quasi-experimental design to analyze if there is a difference in academic performance of students taught with traditional method and those taught using the flipped classroom approach. The findings showed there is a significant difference between the performance of students taught in the flipped classroom and those taught in the traditional classroom. The flipped classroom students performed better than the traditional classroom based on these areas; first, students' learning is put in the students' hands-on (Benjamin & Sam, 2012). Secondly, students discovered two opportunities to learn either through video or home work. By this they could apply their knowledge in the classroom. Thirdly, the idea of moving the direct instruction outside the classroom where more time is given in the classroom for more teacher support (Mazur, 1997). The authors went further to examine whether there were gender differentials in the students' academic achievement in control and experimental groups based on gender. However, the result revealed that there was a significant ($p > .05$) difference in students' academic achievement on eight tests for both groups. It was discovered that the male students in the flipped class performed better than their female counterpart in the teacher-centred approach. However, the females in the classroom that was not flipped obtained higher scores on average.

In the same vein, another study conducted by Charles-Ogan and Williams (2015) evaluated the advantages of a flipped classroom over conventional setting in student's academic achievement in Mathematics. They used 100 students in Hallmark Academy in Rivers State involving two groups, experimental and control groups. A video CD offline Mathematics lesson was recorded and administered by the experimental group had a mean gain of 28.60 while the control group had a mean gain of 16.62. They concluded that flipped classroom encourages peer instructions, provides a means of evaluating students understanding and that teaching and learning becomes more exciting when students are directly involved in the learning process.

The Junior Secondary School (JSS) is the second degree of the instructive stepping stool after the grade school in Nigeria. At this level, most guardians start to acknowledge what their wards will get the chance to become beneficial residents. Numerous subjects are taken at this level. Regardless of the program an understudy is attempted, there are various center subjects that all understudies must offer, and among these center subjects is Mathematics. Once more, to move to a more elevated level for senior Secondary education in Nigeria, an understudy is required to pass the center subjects in Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination (JSSCE). It is essential to note in this manner, that inability to perform respectably in any of the center subjects which for this situation concerns Mathematics may end the scholarly yearnings of understudies. It is a direct result of this that all guardians put resources into various ways and in many occurrences including additional educational cost for their wards to perform well.

From the various viewed and reviewed of empirical studies that have been done locally and internationally showed that flipped classroom of instructional strategy enhance effective learning in students in terms of Mathematics which take care and control of their learning directly through practical experiences in group and individual activities while adequate instruction of using flipped classroom in Nigeria was elaborated for its importance since it enhances students' academic achievement not only in Mathematics.

The poor performance of students in Mathematics over the year has been a major concern to educators. The relevance of Mathematics for sustainable development and growth of any nation is not in doubt, people use Mathematics knowingly or unknowingly in the solving of day-to-day problems. In recent times, there have been repeated complaints over dwelling academic achievement of students among students in Nigeria especially senior secondary school students (Obanya, 2009).

The problem of low achievement by students in Mathematics is like a cankerworm that is eating deeper by the day into Nigeria's educational system and is a major hindrance to the technological advancement of the country. Students have responded to this situation in a negative way. Rather than investing energy and time in studying, students direct most of their efforts at looking for ways to cheat in order to pass Mathematics examinations. This is indicated by the high rate of examination malpractice incidents observed at all stages of learning in Nigeria education (Mofinews, 2006). Some students abstain completely from Mathematics classes and perceive attending classes as waste of time. The situation is so deplorable that school principals and teachers can no longer handle or control truant students from Mathematics classes, and all efforts to bring these students to see the need to study Mathematics has proved abortive (Bassey, 2002).

Literatures have shown that Mathematics is a model of thinking and a very crucial tool in both science and arts, while a great deal of efforts may have been devoted to the influence of learning environment variables such as teacher quality, instructional facilities and class size. But from different observation reveals that teacher centred-method has dominated the teaching of Mathematics. Okri and Aglazor (2020) observed that in most cases, the approach is teacher-centred and didactic in nature, whereby the students simply listen, copy notes, do class work and assignments, as a result, these students are passive which in the long run affects their capacity to retain the fundamental concepts. Therefore, there is need to employ other innovative strategies which will benefit the schools and the society at large. This study therefore, seeks to find out the effect of flipped strategy on achievement in algebraic concepts among secondary school students in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of flipped strategy on achievement in algebraic concepts among secondary school students in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the difference in mean achievement scores of government secondary school students taught concept algebra using flipped instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State?
2. Determine the difference in mean achievement scores of government secondary school male and female students taught concept algebra using flipped instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of government secondary school students taught concept of algebra using flipped instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of government secondary school male and female students taught concept of algebra using flipped instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State.

Methodology

Quasi-experimental research design was explored for this study deemed adequate because it is applied to a situation which is not purely experimental in involving human beings especially when all the treatment for validity cannot be controlled. This design was adopted because it is not possible to have complete randomization of subjects. Intact classes were randomly assigned to experimental and control groups. The students who participated in the study received treatment in their classes or were used as control in their classes without re-arranging the class setting. Participants in the control group (C) did not receive treatment while the treatment group (E) received flipped instructional classroom strategy in which pre-test and post -test were administered to the two groups respectively. Hence, two groups were involved in the study; the treatment and the control groups. The treatment group was one group in which students received instruction on flipped instructional classroom strategy while the control group received instruction on the conventional instructional strategy named teacher centred approach. This design was chosen because it controls the internal validity threat of the initial group equivalence and researcher's selection bias, since there was no randomization of the subjects into group.

The target population includes all senior secondary school two (SS II) in public secondary schools in Ikom education zone of Cross River State. In this study, the purposive multi-stage random sampling technique was utilized. The first stage of sampling requires to randomly draw one (1) co-education public schools out of the 86 in Ikom education zone by ballot approach. The next stage involved the random sampling of one class in the school for the experiment. Treatment was randomly assigned to each of the two groups of students that resulted from the sampling of schools and class. This sampling technique

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controlled for location, school type and teachers' qualification were not introduced which might cause bias into the study. Although all the students in a sampled school were present in the class doing the experiment and after treatment a post-test was given to the subjects.

The sample size for this study consists of eighty-three (83) senior secondary school two (SS II) students. This sample was made up of 42 male and 41 female students. Out of the 83 students 31 were below 15 years of age, 30 were between 15-16 years while 12 were above 16 years of age.

Table 1: Sample distribution

Treatment	Male	Female	Total
Experimental	22	20	42
Control	23	18	41
Total	45	38	83

The study used two instruments. These are Students' effective learning of Mathematics questionnaire (SELMQ) and Students' Mathematics Achievement test (SMAT). The instruments were developed by researcher. The SELMQ consisting of 16 items to assess the effective participation of students in learning mathematics, which was developed by the researchers. It has 4-point Likert type response scale in which respondents were expected to indicate (√) in the column against each of the items as it is applied to each other.

The student's mathematical achievement test (SMAT) was developed and put into consideration some certain items in terms of content, test blue print. The mathematics content in which test was considered are (1) number and numeration (2) trigonometry (3) probability (4) simultaneous equation (5) geometry. Data collected was analyzed using inferential statistics. Whereas, hypothesis one was tested with analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) using the pretest as a covariate, the second null hypothesis was analyzed using linear multiple regression statistic. The threshold for decision was set at the 0.05 confidence.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of government secondary school students taught concept of algebra using flipped instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State.

Table 2: Summary of the results of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of the effect of instructional strategy on students' academic achievement in Mathematics

Source of variation	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1474.358	2	737.179	23.487	.000	.367
Intercept	14096.671	1	14096.671	449.125	.000	.847
Pretest	7.679	1	7.679	.245	.622	.003
InstrStrat	1474.351	1	1474.351	46.973	.000	.367
Error	2542.345	81	31.387			
Total	274317.000	84				
Corrected Total	4016.702	83				

As shown in Table 2, the calculated F value for the main effect for instructional strategy is 46.973 and it is statistically significant ($p=.000 < .05$). This means that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean academic achievement of students taught with flipped classroom instructional strategy and those taught with teacher-centred approach when the posttest scores are adjusted for the pretest scores. Since the adjusted mean academic achievement of students taught with flipped classroom instructional strategy ($X_{adj} = 60.926$, $SE = .866$) is higher than that of those taught with teacher-centred approach ($X_{adj} = 52.526$, $SE = .866$), it means that flipped classroom instructional strategy has a significantly greater effect on students' academic achievement in Mathematics than the teacher-centred approach. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of government secondary school male and female students taught concept of algebra using flipped instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Ikrom Education Zone of Cross River State.

Table 3: First-order inter-correlation of the independent and dependent variables

	Post Test	Instructional Strategy	Pretest	Age	Gender
Academic achievement	1.000	-.604a*	.001	.095	-.058
Instructional Strategy	.000b	1.000	.070	.012	.024
Pretest	.495	.263	1.000	-.164	.132
Age	.195	.456	.068	1.000	-.226*
Gender	.301	.415	.116	.019	1.000

The results in the table indicate that only the relationships between academic achievement and age ($r = -.604, p = .000$) and age and gender ($r = -.226, p = .019$) are statistically significant at .05 significance level.

Table 4: Regression ANOVA and regression statistics of the variables

Source of variation	SS	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.level
Regression	1527.094	4	381.773	12.114	.000b
Residual	2489.609	79	31.514		
Total	4016.702	83			

Independent variables	Unstandardized coefficient B	Std error	Standardized coefficient Beta	T	Sig
(Constant)	56.306	11.322		4.973	.000
Instructional Strategy	-8.429	1.229	-.610	-6.861*	.000
Pretest	.059	.082	.065	.721	.473
Age	.768	.658	.107	1.167	.247
Gender	-.381	1.264	-.028	-.302	.764

* $p < .05$, $R = .617$, $R^2 = .380$

The multiple correlation coefficient is .617 which means that only 38% (i.e $R^2 \times 100\%$) of the variance in students' academic achievement in Mathematics can be accounted for by students' age, gender, pretest scores and the instructional strategy used in teaching them. Since the calculated F for the regression ANOVA ($F = 12.114, p = .000$) is statistically significant it means the multiple correlation coefficient is statistically significant. Again, the significant F value indicates that at least one of the independent variables significantly account for the variance in students' academic achievement in Mathematics. A perusal of the regression statistics shows that only the regression coefficient for instructional strategy ($\beta = -.610, t = -6.861, p = .000$) is statistically significant. That means the variance in students' academic achievement in Mathematics can only be significantly accounted for by the instructional strategy used in teaching the students.

Discussion of findings

The result from Table 3 showed that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean academic achievement of students taught with flipped class instructional strategy and those taught with teacher-centred approach when the post-test scores are adjusted for the pretest scores. Since the adjusted mean academic achievement of students taught with flipped classroom instructional strategy ($X_{adj} = 60.926; SE = .866$) is higher than that of those taught with teacher centred approach ($X_{adj} = 52.526; SE = .866$), it means that flipped classroom instructional strategy has a significantly greater effect on students' academic in mathematics than the teacher-centred approach.

The present result is in agreement with the result of Kaushai, Chang-Nan and Chunyen (2015) in their study the impact of flipped classroom on Mathematics concept learning in high school used a pre-test, post-test, quasi experimental design. They used 82 high school students aged between 14-15 years for the study. The experimental group was 41 (28 male and 13 female) and the control group 41 (24 male and 17 female). They categorized the achievers in each group into high, average and low. Those students who scored 75-100 were termed high achievers, those in the bracket of 60-74 were categorized into average

achievers while those below 60 were marked as low achievers. The experimental group was taught trigonometry using the flipped classroom strategy whereas the control group did the same lesson using the conventional learning strategy. The researchers gave both groups a pre-test and post-test with the intention to determine if the learning outcome would be the same using the same instructor. The result showed that the students in experimental group who used flipped classroom strategy performed much better than those who were taught in controlled group. Besides, the study threw more light on the performance of low achievers in the experimental group.

In another work, Kadry and ElHani (2014) used flipped classroom model method for calculus II. The students' performances in the examination were used to assess the scores from 0-100 points. The number of participants who completed the quiz was 120. The performance of the students in the flipped classroom was better than the traditional approach. The performance between male and female model for 60 students was examined. The females in the flipped classroom model performed better. Although the mean scores were higher in the flipped classrooms, the t-test for independent samples proved that the difference in the means between the groups were not significant ($p > .05$). Also, Schultz, Duffield, Rasmuseuin and Wageman (2013) carried out research on effects of flipped classroom model on students' performance for advanced placement high school chemistry students. The research made use of mixed method approach comprising quantitative and qualitative techniques. They used quasi-experimental design to analyze if there is a difference in academic performance of students taught with traditional method and those taught using the flipped classroom approach. The findings showed there is a significant difference between the performance of students taught in the flipped classroom and those taught in the traditional classroom.

From Table 4, the results in the table indicates that only the relationship between academic achievement and age ($r = .604$, $p = .000$) and age and gender ($r = .226$, $p = .019$) are statistically significant at .05 significance level. The result is in agreement with Saunders (2014) who explained that pedagogical pattern of the teacher is very important to students' academic achievement and it can greatly impact on the way students view a particular subject and even education as a whole, he observed that teachers represent their subjects anytime and everywhere and so, the way they teach would encourage or discourage the students from studying the subjects. Also Vaughan (2014) stated that flipped model of instruction provides educators with the means to integrate effective use of technology in their classrooms to promote an active, collaborative environment. The results of the study revealed that flipped classroom improves students' engagement, increase students-teacher feedback and promote self-pace learning among students.

Conclusion

The concludes that flipped instructional strategy had significant effect on achievement in algebra concepts hence, can be employed in teaching by Mathematics teachers in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Cross River State Secondary School Education Board should deemed consider implementing the flipped classroom instructional strategy in mathematics as it engages students' dedication, interest and motivation in learning.
2. The state government and education stakeholders should also provide training programmes for students and teachers on information and communication technology (ICT) integration into mathematics curriculum which will serve as an antidote to enhance teaching and learning of mathematics effectively.
3. Schools should be adequately equipped with gadgets and technological infrastructural facilities to pave way for the implementation of flipped classroom instruction in the teaching and learning of mathematics.
4. Also, the flipped classroom instructional strategy is a developing pedagogy, therefore, there is need for research to include all students of different ages.

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